

TOWARDS THE PEDIATRIC HEALTH DATA SPACE (PHDS)

Overview

The Pediatric Health Data Space (PHDS) will be a trusted digital ecosystem designed to address the unique challenges of pediatric healthcare through secure, privacy-preserving data sharing. Building on the PHEMS project, PHDS will enable collaborative research, cross-border benchmarking, and innovation while keeping hospitals in full control of their data. Guided by principles of efficiency, security, scalability, sustainability, and compliance, PHDS will align closely with the European Health Data Space (EHDS), ensuring interoperability and regulatory readiness.

What are Data Spaces?

Data Spaces are collaborative digital ecosystems that allow different organizations to share, access, and reuse data in a controlled, secure, and interoperable way. They operate on common technical standards, governance models, and trust frameworks to ensure transparency and data sovereignty.

In a Data Space, each participant retains control over its own data while benefiting from the ability to pool information for broader purposes. By establishing rules of trust, privacy, and security, Data Spaces support responsible data sharing across sectors and borders.

Understanding the Pediatric Health Data Space (PHDS)

Pediatric healthcare faces unique data challenges that require collaborative solutions. Many pediatric conditions, especially rare and complex diseases, affect small patient populations, making data sharing essential to achieve the statistical power needed for research. Cross-border benchmarking of clinical care and operational performance is also crucial, particularly in highly specialized (tertiary) care, to improve quality and outcomes.

Furthermore, the evaluation of new therapies for rare and orphan diseases depends on real-world evidence collected after market introduction, while the development of advance analytical tools and AI

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or machine learning requires large, diverse, and well-coordinated datasets.

To meet these needs, partners of the PHEMS project are working to establish **the Pediatric Health Data Space (PHDS) - a trusted, privacy-preserving ecosystem for sharing pediatric health data.**

Building on the technical infrastructure and governance model developed by the PHEMS project, PHDS will enable ethical, effective, and scalable secondary use of health data, supporting research, benchmarking, and innovation in pediatric care.

PHDS Architecture

The PHDS will be designed as a specialized data space - a collaborative digital ecosystem where organizations share data under uniform rules, with certified participants and strong trust frameworks. In healthcare, such data spaces are established through a combination of legislation and contractual agreements.

PHDS will be built on five main design principles:

- 1. Control:** Keeps full decision-making authority with the data holders.
- 2. Security:** Ensure all data stays within hospital-controlled environments.
- 3. Sustainability:** Supports long-term operation through adaptable business models.
- 4. Scalability:** Can grow in participants, use cases, and data volume without systemic redesign.
- 5. Efficiency:** Automates workflows for research and benchmarking, reducing time and effort.

An additional **core design principle is alignment with EHDS requirements**, including metadata standards and catalogues, permit processes, and certified secure processing environments. This ensures that investments made by hospitals as data controllers in PHDS also meet EHDS compliance.

To maintain trust, PHDS will use **digital identity verification, role-based access controls**, and

neutral governance, ensuring transparent and fair participation for all members.

PHDS will be designed to meet the specific needs of children's hospitals. It enables clinical benchmarking and cross-borders research while respecting diverse legal frameworks across Europe

By keeping data within hospital environments and enabling only the secure sharing of aggregated results, PHDS will ensure **compliance with GDPR, national laws, and internal hospital policies.**

Governance and Participation

The PHDS will be established through legal agreements among participating entities, initially including hospitals involved in the PHEMS project and at the European Children's Hospitals Organization (ECHO), which represents a broad network of pediatric hospitals across Europe.

ECHO, a neutral non-profit association of leading children's hospitals, will oversee PHDS governance, ensuring independence, inclusivity, and accountability.

Participation will be structured on two levels:

- **Full Participants**, primarily ECHO-affiliated hospitals, play an active role in governance and infrastructure development.
- **Associated Participants**, such as research institutions and technology providers, engage in specific projects and services under PHDS rules.

This governance model will ensure flexibility while maintaining strong governance and trust among participants.

Real-World Impact: Hospital Benchmarking Use Case

Hospital benchmarking will be one of the first and most impactful applications of the PHDS. Benchmarking enables pediatric hospitals to compare the quality, performance, and

operational efficiency of their services, providing actionable insights that drive continuous improvement in patient care and hospital operations.

Traditionally, cross-border performance comparison has been slow and inconsistent, requiring manual data collection and non-standardized metrics. PHDS will transform this process by automating data extraction from electronic health records (EHRs), applying continuous, privacy-preserving performance analysis. This will give hospitals faster access to reliable insights, supports better clinical decisions, and informs more effective strategies for quality improvement.

Through this structured framework, **hospitals can identify best practices, improve patient outcomes, and optimize resource allocation while maintaining full control of their data and safeguarding patient confidentiality.**

How PHDS related to EHDS

The European Health Data Space (EHDS), formally adopted in 2024, establishes a unified legal and technical framework for the primary and secondary use of health data across EU member states. It facilitates patient access for their health records, promotes seamless cross-border data exchange for clinical care, and ensure that health data is used securely and ethically for research, innovation, and public policy.

The **PHDS** will be designed to be **fully compatible with the EHDS**, serving as a practical implementation of its principles within the pediatric healthcare sector. PHDS is designed to closely align with the standards set by the EHDS, ensuring compliance in areas such as data discovery through standardized metadata and catalogues, harmonized data permit procedures with clear template and evaluation criteria, and the use of secure processing environments that meet the necessary technical specifications and certification requirements where applicable.

Joining the PHDS Community

Through the PHEMS project, PHDS will be established as a long-term, sustainable platform for health data collaboration in pediatrics.

PHDS will invite:

- **Hospitals and clinicians** to participate in benchmarking and data collaboration.
- **Researchers** to engage in privacy-preserving federated studies.
- **Technology providers** to support secure data infrastructure.
- **Policy stakeholders** to shape a scalable model for European health data sharing.

Together, we can create a data space that not only meets regulatory expectations but also transformns pediatric care for generations to come.

Key Takeaways

The PHDS will establish a trusted and privacy-preserving ecosystem for sharing secondary pediatric health data, supporting research, benchmarking, and innovation.

It will be built on strong principles of data control, security, scalability, and **alignment with EHDS standards**, ensuring ethical, compliant, and secure data use.

The initiative will be governed by ECHO, with clear roles for full and associated participants, promoting transparent, inclusive, and accountable collaboration across Europe.

The first real-world applications, such as cardiology benchmarking, sepsis prediction, and hemophilia treatment, will demonstrate how PHDS can drive data-informed improvements in pediatric care while maintaining patient privacy.